

How Artifacts Acquire Agency

Mark Thomas Young

Abstract: It is common to view the technologies that surround us as either tools or machines. This distinction is often understood to reflect a difference between kinds of technology: those which operate by human agency, and those which operate by their own, technological form of performative agency. This paper aims to explore how common arguments for the performative agency of machines ultimately fail to establish the claim that anything other than humans are capable of performing tasks. In light of such problems, I will propose an alternative conception which understands machines to be distinguished by the way in which the human agency on which they depend is concealed. After examining reasons why we should consider this concealment to represent a social rather than technological phenomenon, this paper concludes by exploring implications this view holds for the way in which the ethics of automation is approached in the philosophy of technology.

Keywords: Automation, agency, ethics of automation, work, hidden labor

1. Introduction

When we consider the range of different technologies that surround us, it is common to draw a distinction between those we understand as tools: technologies that we use to perform work, such as the keyboard on which I am typing, and those we understand as machines: technologies that perform work *for* us—such as the dishwasher operating in the background or the robot vacuum cleaner making its way slowly across the floor. This way of distinguishing between tools and machines is so deeply ingrained in common ways of thinking and acting in relation to technology, that it is rarely, if ever, raised as a subject of discussion itself. Yet despite

the fact that this distinction is so intuitive, we might nonetheless ask if it actually makes sense. Can devices or machines really perform work for us?

In order to clarify my question, it is worth noting that the sense of work I am referring to here is not that which Bertrand Russell jokingly referred to as either “altering the position of matter at or near the earth’s surface” or “telling other people to do so” (Russell 2004, 3). Instead, I simply mean the capacity of a machine to perform a task, such as washing dishes or vacuuming a floor. If this sounds like a strange question to ask, its most likely due to the fact that it’s long been common to assume that machines can perform work in this sense. In fact, to say that this way of thinking about machines is pervasive would be an understatement. Consider for example, the extent to which this idea of machines performing work for humans is coupled closely with conceptions of modernity in western culture, where it is common to understand the wide variety and availability of machines which perform tasks for us as distinguishing us from our premodern forebears, who struggled to perform those same tasks themselves with the help of only rudimentary tools. At least since the enlightenment, narratives of technological progress have often been framed around the idea of machines achieving feats impossible for humans, relieving us of work or even taking our jobs altogether. Today, the idea of machines performing work for us is bolstered simply by the fact that when we glance over the technologies that currently surround us in our homes, such as the dishwasher or robot vacuum cleaner for example, we are confronted with a variety of devices that certainly appear to perform work for us.

Indeed, this way of conceptualizing the operation of certain kinds of technology is so intuitive that we rarely, if ever stop to consider (a) what it means to say that a device or machine can perform work for us or (b) whether it makes sense to attribute this kind of capacity to a technology in the first place. The neglect of such questions is widespread and applies no less within the philosophy of technology. This should surprise us, considering how fond philosophers are of exploring questions concerning whether technology can do the kinds of things humans can do. Yet while much ink has been spent debating whether certain technologies are able to think as we do, or make decisions as we do, few philosophers, if any, have stopped to address the more fundamental question of whether a technology, rather than a human, should be understood as able to *do* anything at all. In other words, to what extent does it make sense to understand a technology, rather than a human, as being responsible for the performance of a task? It is this question that I will consider in this article.

The first section examines how modern conceptions of the distinction between tools and machines understands the latter to be distinguished by their capacity to perform tasks independently of human agents. After identifying this performative conception of technological agency in existing literature on technology in philosophy and sociology, I will adopt a more critical stance in the second section by drawing attention to problems inherent in common arguments for the idea that certain technologies can be understood to perform work for us. In light of these problems, I will in the third section advance an alternative conception of what it means to draw a distinction between tools and machines that does not ascribe performative agency to artifacts. The paper will conclude by exploring some implications this view holds for how the ethics of automation is currently approached in the philosophy of technology.

2. The Tool—Machine Distinction

Around the turn of the nineteenth century, the idea that machines are capable of performing work emerged as a dominant theme that was expressed in different ways through the writings of commentators on the industrial revolution. In light of the sudden and deep changes which occurred to technology and work during this time, many thinkers came to understand the new forms of industrial machinery to be radically different from the technologies that had come before. In *Capital*, for example, Karl Marx expressed this view through a contrast between tools and machines. Against those “mathematicians and experts on mechanics” who fail to recognize the difference between tools and machines, Marx argued that a machine should be understood as:

a mechanism that, after being set in motion, performs with its tools the same operations as the worker formerly did with similar tools. Whether the motive power is derived from man, or in tum from a machine, makes no difference here. From the moment that the tool proper is taken from man and fitted into a mechanism, a machine takes the place of a mere implement. (Marx 1990, 495)

By highlighting the self-acting character of machines through a contrast to tools, Marx followed Georg W. F. Hegel who had earlier suggested that:

a tool does not yet have the activity within it. It is an inert thing; it does not turn back into itself. I must still work with it. [In order to make a machine] the tool’s activity must be placed within the tool itself, so that it is made self-acting. . . . In general, its passivity is transformed into activity, in

persistent collaboration. Above all, it happens also (b) in that nature's own activity be employed—the elasticity of the watchspring, (the power of) water, wind—so that, in their sensory existence, these do something other than what they (ordinarily) would do. (Hegel 1983, 103)¹

It is from this way of conceiving of machines as self-acting that we derive what Carl Mitcham has described as the “common notion” of the distinction between tools and machines; that a tool is something humanly manipulated, whereas a machine “denotes an instrument in its independence, or that aspect of an instrument that is not dependent on the human” (Mitcham 1994, 167).

Mitcham was right to suggest that understanding the machine in terms of an independence from humans was common. Literature on technology throughout the twentieth century reveals numerous examples of authors employing this idea to distinguish tools from machines. In the opening pages of *Technics and Civilization*, for example, Lewis Mumford distinguishes machines from tools in exactly this way: “The essential distinction between a machine and a tool lies in the degree of independence in the operation from the skill and motive power of the operator: the tool lends itself to manipulation, the machine to automatic action” (Mumford 1934, 2). In exploring the role and significance of the computer in Western culture for example, media theorist David J. Bolter, also employed the idea of the machine as operating independently from humans to distinguish tools and machines, by claiming that:

A machine is characterized by sustained, autonomous action. It is set up by human hands and then is more or less set loose from human control . . . such is the steam engine, which turns coal into power to move ships or pump water without the intervention of human muscles. A tool, unlike a machine, is not self-sufficient or autonomous in action. (Bolter 1984, 233)

Today, the forms of technology that are most commonly understood to embody this concept of the machine are found in robotics and artificial intelligence, applications of which are widely considered to function without human involvement.² The idea that such technologies possess performative agency even finds implicit articulation in definitions of automation itself as “machines, tools, devices, installations and systems that are all platforms developed by humans to *perform* a given set of activities *without human involvement* during those activities” (Nof 2009, 14 emphasis added).

It is clear from what we have seen so far that these different formulations of the distinction between tools and machines all draw upon an interpretation of

independence in terms of performance; in each case, machines are suggested to *perform* independently of humans. For this reason, we can understand the tool-machine distinction as attributing a form of agency to machines; however, this is not the notion of agency common in the western philosophical tradition, which understands the possession of intentional states to be a necessary condition for the performance of actions (Gunkel 2012). It is because conceptions of agency have traditionally been restricted to beings capable of intentional states such as beliefs and desires that much of the existing philosophical literature on the question of machine agency centers on the investigation of whether machines should also be considered to possess intentional states and what implications this may have for the attribution of moral responsibility.

The form of agency the tool-machine distinction attributes to technology however is more basic. A dishwasher can be considered responsible for performing the task of washing your dishes, without being considered morally responsible for the washing your dishes. In fact, this more basic conception of performative agency can be understood as a necessary condition for the attribution of intentional agency. Before it can be considered reasonable to consider a technology *morally* responsible for performing a particular task, it must first be established that it is not humans, but rather the technology itself that is responsible for the performance of the task.

While discussions of this more basic form of machine agency are largely absent from philosophy, this is not true of all disciplinary approaches to technology. The most developed account of this conception of technological agency can be found in sociology, in particular the work of Andrew Pickering, who contests the idea that only humans can be considered genuine agents by arguing for a paradigm shift in which we:

change our conception of agency in a way that enables us to come at the world from a new angle. We should stop thinking about agency in terms of will, intention, calculation and representation, and start thinking about it in terms of performance, in terms of doing things, things that are consequential (sic) in the world. Performance is the place we should start from, not reason, language, representations and symbols [. . .] We humans are performative agents—we do things in the world—but so do rocks and stones, cats and TV sets, stars and machine tools. At the level of performance, we are the same as everything else; we are not different in kind. (Pickering 2013, 26)

Those familiar with STS will immediately recognize similarities here to conceptions of material agency in actor network theory (ANT) as the capacity of an entity to make or promote a difference in another entity or network (Sayes 2013). However, in order to capture the specific sense of agency the tool-machine distinction attributes to technology we must go one step further. For in order to become technological, material agency must be *captured*, a process which Pickering describes as getting the material world to do something for you (Pickering 1995b, xi). Not surprisingly, in selecting the most vivid illustration of this process, Pickering looks to the same place as did earlier proponents of the tool-machine distinction—industrial machinery, which he characterizes as the site of the capture of material agency *par excellence* (Pickering 1995a).

In this section, we have seen how the tool-machine distinction involves a sense of technological agency which captures at once both *more* than the minimal notion of material agency offered by ANT and *less* than the intentional conception of agency common in the philosophy of technology. Now that we have a clearer understanding of the way in which the distinction distinguishes machines from tools, we can turn our attention to exploring what reasons we have for thinking that such a distinction corresponds to actual differences between kinds of technologies. In the next section, we will examine common arguments for the idea that certain technologies can be understood to possess performative agency and explore the challenges they face.

3. Why Technology Doesn't Work

We don't need to look very far in order to find the influence of the tool-machine distinction on our understanding of the development of modern technology. The idea that the industrial revolution saw the emergence of new forms of technology which could perform work independently of humans is clearly visible in descriptions of the Newcomen steam engine as a wholly new type of machine because it “could run in the absence of a human operator” (Lovelock 2019, 52), or suggestions that with the invention of the power loom “machines now did work that had previously been done by hand” (Kidner et al 2014, 553). And it's not only industrial technology that is conceived in this way. Because the modernization of the home has traditionally been understood on the model of industrialization, this has inevitably affected the ways in which we have come to think about domestic technologies, which have often been described in similar terms. Throughout the twentieth century for example, domestic appliances such as washing machines and bread makers were regularly advertised as taking care of housework on their own.³

Today similar descriptions are frequently applied to domestic robots such as robot vacuum cleaners and lawn mowers, the latter of which are sometimes described as being able to “cut several thousand meters of grass, entirely without human involvement” (Lee 2020, 20).

Yet despite providing us with one of our most pervasive and enduring conceptions of technological agency, the tool-machine distinction is more problematic than may appear at first glance. For while the idea that certain forms of technology can be distinguished by their independence from human agents may be intuitively plausible, stating exactly what this independence consists in is much easier said than done. After all, human agents play an undeniably necessary role in enabling the operation of all forms of technology, from Newcomen engines to robot lawn mowers. Indeed, the problems involved in distinguishing machines from tools have long been recognized even among proponents of the tool-machine distinction itself.⁴ In what follows, we will examine some of these problems by exploring two arguments commonly considered to support of the idea that certain forms of technology possess performative agency.

The first argument that we will consider concerns what cultural theorist Sianne Ngai has described as the “simplest promise of all technology [. . .] the reduction of labor by way of a device” (Ngai 2020, 55). The potential of new technologies to reduce our involvement in the performance of certain tasks is one of the most common and intuitive reasons for thinking that machines can perform work. For example, one of the reasons that people value robot vacuum cleaners so highly, is that they understand what it is like to perform the vacuuming with an electric vacuum cleaner. While a robot vacuum cleaner may still require us to perform certain tasks, such as emptying the dustbin periodically, the extent to which this technology appears to reduce the time people spend directly involved in the task of vacuuming makes it natural to think that the machine itself performs most, if not all of this work *for us*. This way of thinking highlights what I call the *argument from human involvement* which holds that if the introduction of a technology reduces human involvement in the performance of a task while leaving levels of productivity unchanged, then it makes sense to think of the device or machine itself as performing at least some of the work. As we have seen, arguments of this kind often form an implicit component of common understandings of automation as forms of technology that operate without human involvement.

Yet while this way of understanding the operation of certain technologies is common, it faces several problems when used as an argument for the existence of performative technological agency. The first problem is that simply because

a device reduces *our* labour does not necessarily mean that it reduces *all* human labour. The argument above, for example, overlooks labour performed by others, elsewhere, which contributes *directly* to the operation of the robot vacuum cleaner such as the production of software updates that ensure the compatibility of the operating system with software on peripheral devices. The argument above also overlooks activities that *indirectly* contribute to the operation of the device such as the production of electricity or the establishment and maintenance of internet connections. Together these activities can be understood to represent forms of human involvement which have been repositioned by the introduction of the technology.

I use the term “repositioning” here to capture the way in which the adoption and use of new technologies both eliminates certain forms of human activity while at the same time establishing the requirement for new forms of human practice. Because they alter the way activities are performed, all technological change can be understood to involve the repositioning of human involvement to some extent. For example, consider the introduction of automating technologies in the U.S automotive industry after the second world war. Whereas previous systems of production had required workers themselves to transfer parts between machines, new automated assembly lines instead employed systems of interlinked transfer machines for this purpose. However, because the new system could only function when every part was working correctly, it also required new forms of surveillance, record keeping and maintenance to prevent a single component’s failure from causing the entire system to grind to a halt. As historian of technology David Edgerton notes, the transition to the new technologies must for this reason be understood in terms of a repositioning of human activity:

“To a significant extent the transfer machine did not eliminate labour, but transferred it from production to maintenance, away from the tedious work of manning machines to the skilled and more varied work of maintenance” (Edgerton 2006, 86). The tendency for technological changes to reposition rather than eliminate human labour was also recognized by Marx, who suggested that the transition from tools to machines resulted not only in the loss of certain forms of activity but also the acquisition of new forms of practice whereby “the human comes to relate more as watchman and regulator to the production process itself” (Marx 1993, 705), by “watching the machine with his eyes and correcting its mistakes with his hands” (Marx 1990, 496). We will return to explore repositioning in more detail later, but for now let us note how it is common to overlook forms of human involvement that have been repositioned through technological change. However, while this represents a common weakness in arguments from involvement, it is

important to recognize that such failures do not by themselves prevent this form of argument from being used in support of the claim that technologies possess performative agency. After all, if it might be argued that even after widening the scope of the argument to ensure that all forms of human involvement are considered in the operation of a technology, that human involvement is *still* reduced.

However, in order to see why this argument still fails, we will need to put aside for the moment the obvious difficulties involved in attempting to quantify, select, and compare human involvement in the operation of different technologies, and focus instead on the significance of the reduction of human involvement itself. The problem I am referring to here was recognized already by early proponents of the tool-machine distinction, such as the historian Paul Mantoux, who argued that the reduction of human involvement cannot form the basis of a distinction between tools and machines, because the former also reduce human involvement in the performance of a task:

Can we define a machine as something that not only helps, but does away with and replaces human labour? The answer is that the simplest tool saves a considerable amount of labour. A man with a spade will do as much work as twenty men who only have their nails to scratch the ground with. (Mantoux 1929, 193)

That the reduction of human involvement is by itself insufficient to demonstrate the existence of performative agency becomes obvious when we reflect how human involvement is reduced by all kinds of things, many of which aren't really *things* at all. Imagine for example that someone is attempting to clean bread tins by scrubbing them first with soap and then rinsing them in warm water. After an observer suggests that they soak the dishes in the water first, they discover that the time and energy they need to spend cleaning the tins is drastically reduced. Yet what has been introduced in this example is not a new technology, but rather a new technique. The problem with arguments from involvement then, is that they ultimately fail to capture the distinction between technologies which are considered to perform work and those that don't: if we must ascribe agency to anything which reduces human involvement in the performance of a task, then we end up having to ascribe agency not only to machines but to all kinds of things too such as tools, tips, and tricks as well.

As we have seen, Mantoux was well aware of the limitations inherent in attempting to establish the performative agency of certain technologies on the basis of their capacity to reduce the labour required of human agents. As Mantoux

himself noted, even “the most automatic machine does not entirely do away with the human element, for it needs a man to look after it” (Mantoux 1929, 193). For this reason, instead of premising his argument for the performative agency of machines on the basis of an overall reduction of human involvement, Mantoux followed Marx by focusing instead on the reduction of specific forms of human involvement: those that control the operation of a technology:

[while] the workman in charge of such a machine has to start it, stop it, feed it, and keep it in working order . . . he has no part in the actual work it does, save to speed it up, or at most, to see that it works smoothly without jerks or stoppages. His activity or negligence alter the quantity of work done by the machine still more than the quality. He does not do the work, but is only there to regulate and measure it. (Mantoux 1929, 193)

Here we find a different kind of argument for the performative agency of technology that resonates with common ways of understanding automating technologies. When we use an electric vacuum cleaner to clean our house for example, it is we who decides and controls the movements the technology makes. This forms the basis for a contrast to devices such as robot vacuum cleaners, which often move in ways that we do not decide or control. According to this line of reasoning, which I call the *argument from autonomy*, when a technological change reduces the amount of human control over the way a task is performed, the new technology can be considered to perform some, or all of the work by itself.

However, while arguments from autonomy may appear to provide more convincing reasons for thinking that technology is also capable of performing work, they are nonetheless susceptible to a range of problems similar to those faced by the argument from involvement. In the first place, they also typically overlook what can be considered forms of control exercised by other human agents, at other times. For while we as consumers may not decide the exact path a robot vacuum cleaner takes in its journey around the house, much of the behaviour of the device can nonetheless be understood as determined in advance through the design of both software and hardware which control not only the way the device approaches the task of cleaning certain areas but also how it responds to the presence of unforeseen obstacles and so forth. Indeed, as William Haselager notes, robots require an “enormous amount of human off-line involvement (i.e., the programming and designing of the robot) in advance of the robot’s functioning, particularly in relation to which goals the robots should pursue” (Haselager 2005, 519). In his book *Our Robots, Ourselves*, David A. Mindell builds on these insights in developing a

general critique of what he terms the “myth of autonomy” within robotics, arguing that:

For the twenty-first century, then, autonomy is human action removed in time. This, in a sense, is the essence of the term “programming”—telling the computer what to do at some point in the future, when the program is run. Of course the machine will respond to its environment, and may encounter novel situations, and may even develop unexpected behaviors. But the constraints on those behaviors are still very tight, and very much pre-scripted by the designers and programmers. (Mindell 2015, 318)

Recognizing the extent to which the operation of robots are determined by such activities undermines the argument from autonomy by revealing how human control is repositioned rather than reduced in the transition to robotic technology. At the same time, it complicates the task of providing a demonstration of the reduction of human control in the use of robots. For if anything, a much wider range of human agents are involved in influencing the movements of the robot vacuum cleaner from afar, than the traditional vacuum cleaner whose movements are determined solely by a lone human operator. Attempts to define the notion of autonomy within the field of robotics often try to sidestep these problems by employing extremely specific interpretations of control which exclude forms of human involvement performed off-line, such as programming, in order to substantiate their claims for the performative agency of robotic technologies (Haselager 2005).

Yet despite such attempts, there are reasons to think that seeking to establish the performative agency of machines on the basis of reduced human control is a project which faces inherent limitations. After all, the concept of performative agency itself implies a certain degree of human control. Not only are those technologies which are often considered to manifest this form of agency such as robots, designed to perform specific tasks, but they are also intended to do so in specific ways—efficiently and without causing harm to human co-workers, for example. For this reason, it seems unlikely that a technology over which we had *no* control could illustrate the kind of independence captured by the concept of performative agency itself and would most likely, as David A. Mindell notes, be regarded instead as a failure:

the machine that operates entirely independently of human direction is a useless machine. Only a rock is truly autonomous (and even a rock was formed and placed by its environment). Automation changes the type of human involvement required and transforms but does not eliminate it. For any

apparently autonomous system, we can always find the wrapper of human control that makes it useful and returns meaningful data. (Mindell 2015, 14)

In this section we have explored how arguments from involvement and control ultimately fail to establish the performative agency of machines. The difficulties faced by these two arguments highlights how the simple idea that technology can perform work *for us* is much harder to establish than we might have assumed at first. Looking closely at the differences between the way in which tools and machines are designed and operated has revealed that machines are distinguished from tools not by requiring less human involvement—but rather different forms of human involvement. Likewise, we can understand machines to employ different forms of human control rather than less. What this means is that like the electric vacuum cleaner then, the robot vacuum cleaner can also be understood as a tool, albeit one that channels a wider variety of forms of human involvement that may not be immediately obvious and draws upon sources of control that may be removed in time and space. According to this perspective, both technologies can be understood to represent different ways in which humans perform the task of cleaning. By undermining the contention that something other than humans are performing in the construction and operation of machines, this approach stands as a direct challenge to the tool-machine distinction as traditionally construed. However, adopting this perspective requires us to explain why and how we come to draw distinctions between technologies that we use to perform work and those that perform work for us in the first place. This will be our goal in the next section, where we will explore what we can learn from the failures of the above arguments about what it means to ascribe agency to artifacts.

4. How Artifacts Acquire Agency

In the previous section, we explored how two different arguments for the claim that technology can perform work ultimately failed to establish the existence of a form of performative agency distinct to that possessed by human agents. Although each argument adopted a different approach, both can nonetheless be understood to have committed the same kind of error: that of misattributing the agency upon which a technology depends to the device or machine itself rather than the wide range of human agents whose continued activity make its operation possible. Yet despite failing to establish the performative agency of technology, we should be careful not to dismiss these arguments too quickly.

In this section, I want to explore how far from merely representing examples of flawed reasoning, these arguments elucidate something far more important about what it means to describe a technology as a machine. For what I want to suggest is that the errors these arguments commit—that of (a) overlooking the different forms of human agency upon which the operation of a technology depends and (b) re-assigning those capacities to the device or machine itself—highlight the *actual* processes by which certain forms of artifacts come to be ascribed agency. According to this perspective then, the tool-machine distinction corresponds not to differences between kinds of technologies, but rather to differences in the way in which we view or interpret the operation of different technologies. This approach understands the processes by which certain technologies are identified as machines to closely resemble what early anthropologists described as fetishism: a term originally used to capture what was considered to be a primitive practice among indigenous cultures of projecting supernatural powers and intentional purposiveness into inanimate material objects (Pletz 2003). Yet understanding the tool-machine distinction as a form of fetishism in this sense itself raises a host of new questions, chief among these being why it is that only certain technologies come to be ascribed performative agency. Why for example, is it so common to identify the robot vacuum cleaner as a machine, and the power drill as a tool? In other words, why do we fetishize certain technologies, but not others? It is to these questions that we will turn in the present section.

We can begin addressing these questions by examining why certain forms of human involvement come to be overlooked in the operation of a technology. In the last section we noted how all technological change involves the repositioning of human activity in the performance of a specific task. We also noted how the adoption of certain technologies, such as robot vacuum cleaners, lead to human involvement being repositioned in ways that can make it harder to recognize. In contrast to the traditional vacuum cleaner for example, in which the movement of the device is controlled solely by the user, robot vacuum cleaners are guided and controlled not only by their users, but also programmers who are removed in both time and space. In light of such examples, it is tempting to think that repositioning can explain why different forms of human involvement come to be overlooked in the operation of certain technologies. From this perspective, the obfuscation of human involvement appears to be a technological phenomenon—a result of the way the structure and use of new technologies reorganizes and repositions human activities in ways that make them more or less visible. Yet while the design of new technologies clearly plays an important role in leading many to overlook various

forms of human involvement⁵ there are number of reasons why we should resist understanding repositioning itself to be responsible for the erasure of the human labour on which the operation of a technology depends.

In the first place, forms of human involvement which end up being overlooked after repositioning do not necessarily stay hidden. Despite common depictions of artificial intelligence as functioning without human intervention, for example, there is today a growing appreciation not only of the extent to which the use of this technology in various settings depends on labour performed by humans, but also of the conditions under which such labour is performed. Importantly, the increased recognition of these forms of human involvement have occurred not as a result of any change in the design or use of these technologies, but rather due to a growing body of investigative journalism⁶ and academic scholarship⁷ which aims to correct misleading depictions of the capacity of such technologies to perform work on their own. Examples such as this highlight how the visibility of the human involvement on which a technology depends is *not* determined by the structure or arrangement of a technology itself, but rather emerges as a result of social processes in which conflicting interpretations of how a technology operates compete for dominance. Rather than being established once and for all through the design of a technology then, the visibility of the human involvement on which a technology depends is often subject to constant negotiation and is therefore always in the process of being created.

The second reason why we should be reluctant to understand repositioning itself to be responsible for the concealment of human involvement is that the forms of human activity that come to be concealed after repositioning are not restricted only to those performed by people removed in time or space. Often they are right under our noses, and sometimes it is even we who perform them. This applies especially to the wide range of automating technologies which depend on activities performed by consumers. Take for example forms of algorithmic management employed by companies such as Uber and Airbnb, which reposition the various aspects of managing a workforce previously performed by managers such as the evaluation of the job performance of workers or the assessment of the quality of services provided, to consumers themselves who are encouraged to spend their time providing feedback and reviews. As Hamid Ekbia and Bonnie Nardi note, forms of labor such as this are often “hidden, poorly compensated, or uncompensated, and naturalized as part of what it means to be a ‘user’ of digital technology” (Ekbia and Bardi 2017, 1).

Similar insights are revealed by empirical studies examining the adoption of robot vacuum cleaners which illustrate how the work of cleaning is repositioned within the home in the transition to the new technology. While the new technology does indeed eliminate certain forms of work, such as that of dragging a device around behind us or switching electrical outlets when the cord reaches its end, it also requires users to perform a range of new activities that were absent in the use of the traditional vacuum cleaner. In addition to managing the operation of the device through an app, these include keeping cables and wires off the floor, tucking in or taping down the tassel on rugs, removing small objects such as toys and rearranging furniture in order to prevent the device from becoming stuck (Sung et al. 2008; Bauwen and Fink 2012). Sometimes it is also necessary to restrict the area within which the device can move; this might be to prevent it knocking over water bowls for pets for example, or to ensure that a particularly messy area is cleaned thoroughly (Forlizzi and DiSalvo 2006). In such cases barriers are created either from what is on hand, such as cushions and boxes, or by utilizing virtual walls—devices which transmit infrared barriers around certain areas. Interestingly, empirical studies indicate how the activity required to monitor and assist such devices is often interpreted as a form of entertainment rather than work (Sung et al. 2008), thereby reinforcing perceptions of such devices as taking care of housework on their own.

So, while repositioning can indeed be understood to create opportunities for the erasure of different forms of human labor, the tendency to overlook forms of human involvement that are staring us in the face supports the idea that repositioning itself is insufficient to account for the way human involvement comes to be concealed in the operation of certain technologies. Rather than being determined by the way they are designed or used then, the independence of technologies commonly considered to perform work *for us* should be understood to emerge as the result of an interpretive feat, in which certain forms of human involvement are disassociated from the operation of the technology. Indeed, it is only through such an interpretative feat that technologies such as the robot lawn mower could be claimed to operate “entirely without human involvement” (Lee 2020, 20) despite the wide array of human agents who are involved in enabling its operation, for example by scheduling its activity via an app, setting perimeter wires, or producing software updates.

Explaining how certain technologies come to be identified as machines therefore requires us to examine the processes through which we arrive at such interpretations. As we have seen already, these interpretations cannot be understood to be

determined by the design of a technology alone. Rather than seeking technological explanations for the concealment of human involvement then, we must turn our attention instead to the social and political processes which generate and sustain particular interpretations of the role human activity plays in the operation of a technology. In doing so we draw upon insights central to two traditions: feminist studies of technology and sociological studies of work, both of which have long recognized how the visibility of work performed by human beings results from social and political processes.⁸ Through studies exploring how human activity is repositioned and erased throughout particular episodes of technological change, these traditions have contributed to increasing our understanding of the variety of different ways in which discourses and practices surrounding new technologies help to shape interpretations of the human involvement upon which they depend. In what is perhaps the most well-known study of this kind, *More Work for Mother* (1983) Ruth Schwartz Cowan challenged the once prevalent idea that the diffusion of domestic appliances in America throughout the twentieth century eliminated housework. In arguing instead that housework remained relatively constant throughout this period, Cowan sought to account for the different factors which helped cultivate impressions of its eradication, noting that domestic labour:

is difficult to recognize, because the reigning theory of family history tells us that it should not be there, because the reigning methodology of the social sciences cannot be applied to it, because ordinary language has a penchant for masking it, and because advertisers have had a vested interest in convincing us that it has evaporated. (Cowan 1983, 210)

By focusing specifically on gendered forms of labour, examples such as this draw attention to how questions of power are central to the processes by which technologies come to be viewed as possessing performative agency. Because interpretations of the operation of a technology are negotiated rather than given, those with access to the greatest resources can often exert a disproportionate influence on the way in which a technology and the work surrounding it is understood. Marginalized social groups therefore face the greatest risk of having their labour erased, such as we find with content moderators in the global south, or caregivers facilitating the function of therapeutic robotics (Ekbria and Bardi 2017). Furthermore, the practice of erasure itself facilitates new forms of exploitation, for example by enabling employers to subvert labour standards without facing public scrutiny or legal repercussions. In her study of the work performed on crowdsourcing platforms which enable the function of a wide variety of artificial intelligence applica-

tions, Miriam Cherry draws attention to how the way in which the invisibility of such practices “may exacerbate existing trends that undermine or erode labour standards” (Cherry 2016, 84). Similarly, in their study of the labour performed on such platforms, Mary L. Gray and Siddarth Suri remind us that “when little attention is paid to the workers behind these jobs, on-demand labour can quickly become alienating, debasing, precarious and isolating ghost work” (Gray and Suri 2019, xxvi).

Exploring the human involvement behind technologies commonly understood to operate autonomously therefore reveals a range of ethical issues, many of which have rarely been considered in philosophical studies on the ethics of robotics and automation, which are typically framed around addressing problems stemming from the capacity of such technologies to operate without human involvement.⁹ The range of issues commonly considered in such studies, such as the problems of ascribing moral responsibility for the actions of robots or the threat they pose to human employment for example, also serve to reinforce idealized conceptions of technology performing on its own. Considered within a wider context of scholarship on the relation between technology and work, this is not unusual. As Judy Wajcman observes, the authors of a number of well-known studies¹⁰ on automation in economics also “seem blind to the huge, casual, insecure, low paid workforce that powers the wheels of the likes of Google, Amazon, Twitter [and] overlook such classed, gendered, racialized data processing work as if algorithms trained, tuned and augmented themselves like magic” (Wajcman 2017, 124). For this reason, while philosophical studies which take as their starting point the idea that automation and AI function without human involvement may indeed succeed in highlighting important ethical issues such as algorithmic bias or the impact of such technologies on the nature of employment, the way in which they do so can itself be considered ethically problematic to the extent that it reinforces conceptions of such technologies which conceal the range of human activity on which they depend and therefore contribute to processes of marginalization and exploitation. Yet there is no reason why we cannot have our cake and eat it too. Refusing to buy into what Mindell terms the “myth of autonomy” (Mindell 2015) and accepting the role human involvement plays in enabling the operation of technologies commonly presumed to function autonomously does not mean doing away with traditional concerns in the ethics of robotics and AI, but rather approaching them in a different way. After all many, if not all of the ethical problems commonly considered to stem from the capacity of such technologies to operate

autonomously can be addressed just as easily without ascribing the technologies themselves performative agency. As Mindell notes:

Much remains to debate about the ethics and policy of remote assassinations carried out by unmanned aircraft with remote operators, or the privacy concerns with similar devices operating in domestic airspace. But these debates are about the nature, location, and timing of human decisions and actions, not about machines that operate autonomously. (Mindell 2015, 16)

While questions surrounding responsibility may indeed be more complicated for technologies which appear to function autonomously, there are no obvious reasons why the ethical issues surrounding their use cannot be addressed without ascribing performative agency to the technology itself. Similarly, we may continue to debate ethical issues surrounding the fact that often no one, not even the designers of technologies such as AI systems can predict exactly how they will behave, without taking this characteristic to be sufficient to delineate a special class of technology distinguished by the possession of performative agency. After all, emergent or unanticipated effects of technology are ubiquitous and not restricted only to those technologies that we commonly identify as having the capacity to act autonomously.

Yet while we do not lose anything from ethical discussions surrounding technology by dispensing with the idea of performative technological agency, we may stand to gain much instead. Here I'm thinking specifically of a range of issues which have traditionally received little sustained examination in discussions on the ethics of robotics and AI, such as questions surrounding labour, exploitation, and corporate social responsibility. Despite their obvious ethical significance, these concerns have often been obscured by the dominant assumption that it is technology, rather than humans that are responsible for the performance of certain tasks. Thus, the project of reframing such discussions around human rather than technological actions holds genuine potential to help enrich existing discussions on the ethics of technology. While this approach has yet to gain momentum, it should nonetheless represent the next step for a field committed to exploring the full spectrum of ethical issues engendered by the technologies that surround us.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, I have argued that against what is commonly assumed, the distinction between tools and machines cannot be understood on technological grounds but must rather be conceived in terms of social processes in which our conceptions of

the role human action plays in the operation of particular technologies are shaped through practices and discourses, many of which serve the interests of specific social actors. Whether we recognize it or not, we take part in such discourses by producing scholarship on the nature of automation and the unique societal challenges to which it gives rise. For this reason, we need to remain aware that how we choose to approach technology through academic study does not serve to merely observe and describe technologies from afar, but rather contributes to the processes by which particular conceptions of technology are generated and sustained. As I have argued, these conceptions can help to facilitate processes of marginalization and exploitation and for this reason should be considered to hold real societal implications. It is for this reason time that we lay to rest the idea that technology can perform work for us and turn our attention instead to giving credit where credit is due—by acknowledging the humans behind the machine.

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Notes

1. For similar comments see also (Hegel 1991, 232–3).
2. See for example (Gray Suri 2019, 23) (Taylor 2018).
3. See (Krafft 2014) (Wajcman 1991, 99).
4. See for example (Mantoux 1929, 190), (Mumford 1934, 2) (Marx 1990, 496).
5. For detailed accounts of the way in which the design of microwork platforms contributes to rendering labor invisible and reinforces idealized conceptions of AI as operating without human involvement see (Cherry 2016) (Gray and Suri 2019, esp Chap 1).
6. See for example (Newton 2019) (Read 2019).

7. See for example (Gillespie 2018) (Roberts 2019), (Gray and Suri 2019) (Ekbia and Bardi 2017).

8. For an overview of studies of sociological studies of invisible work see (Crain, Poster, and Cherry 2016, esp chap 1) (Wajcman 1991, esp chap 2).

9. For examples of philosophical treatments of the ethics of robotics and AI which fail to challenge such assumptions and address the ethical issues surrounding the hidden labor on which such technologies depend see (Lin, Abney and Bekey 2012) (Bartneck et al. 2021).

10. These include (Brynjolfsson and McAfee 2014), (Susskind and Susskind 2015) (Ford 2015).

References

- Bauwen, Valérie, and Julia Fink. 2012. “Will Your Household Adopt Your New Robot?” *Interactions* 19(60): 61–64.
- Bartneck, Christoph, Christoph Lütge, Alan Wagner, and Sean Welsh, eds. 2021. *An Introduction to Ethics in Robotics and AI*. Cham: Springer.
- Bolter, David J. 1984. *Turing’s Man: Western Culture in the Computer Age*. Chapel Hill: University of North Carolina Press.
- Brynjolfsson, Erik, and Andrew McAfee. 2014. *The Second Machine Age: Work Progress and Prosperity in an Age of Brilliant Technologies*. New York: W.W Norton and Co.
- Cherry, Miriam A. 2016. “Virtual Work and Invisible Labor.” In *Invisible Labor: Hidden Work in the Contemporary World*, ed. Marion Crain, Winfred Poster, and Miriam Cherry, 71–86. Oakland: University of California Press.
- Cowan, Ruth Schwartz. 1983. *More Work for Mother: the Ironies of Household Technology from the Open Hearth to the Microwave*. New York: Basic Books.
- Crain, Marion, Winfred Poster, and Miriam Cherry, eds. 2016. *Invisible Labor: Hidden Work in the Contemporary World*. Oakland: University of California Press.
- Edgerton, David. 2006. *The Shock of the Old: Technology and Global History since 1900*. Great Britain: Profile Books.
- Ekbia, Hamid R., and Bonnie Bardi. 2017. *Heteromation, and Other Stories of Computing and Capitalism*. Massachusetts: MIT Press.
- Ford, Martin. 2015. *Rise of the Robots: Technology and the Threat of a Jobless Future*. New York: Basic Books.
- Forlizzi, Jodi, and Carl DiSalvo. 2006. “Service Robots in the Domestic Environment: A Study of the Roomba Vacuum in the Home.” In *HRI ’06: Proceedings of the 1st ACM SIGCHI/SIGART Conference on Human-Robot Interaction*, 258–65. Salt Lake City, Utah, USA, March 2–3, 2006.

- Gillespie, Tarleton. 2018. *Custodians of the Internet: Platforms, Content Moderation and the Hidden Decisions that Shape Social Media*. Yale University Press: New Haven.
- Gray, Mary L., and Siddarth Suri. 2019. *Preface to Ghost Work: How to Stop Silicon Valley from Building a New Global Underclass*. New York: Harcourt Publishing.
- Gunkel, David J. 2012. *The Machine Question: Critical Perspectives on AI, Robots and Ethics*. Massachusetts: MIT Press, 2012).
- Haselager, William F. G. 2005. "Robotics, philosophy and the problems of autonomy." *Pragmatics & Cognition* 13(3): 515–32.
- Hegel, Georg W. F. 1983. *Hegel and the Human Spirit: A Translation of the Jena Lectures on the Philosophy of Spirit (1805–6) with Commentary*, trans. Leo Rauch. Detroit: Wayne State University Press).
- Hegel, Georg W. F. 1991. *Elements of the Philosophy of Right*, trans. Hugh Barr Nisbet, ed. Allen W. Wood. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Kidner, Frank L., Maria Bucur, Ralph Mathisen, Sally McKee, and Theodore R. Weeks, eds. 2014. *Making Europe: The Story of the West*, 2nd ed. Boston: Wadsworth & Cengage Learning.
- Krafft, Andrea. 2014. "Appliance Reliance: Domestic Technologies and the Depersonalization of Housework in Postwar American Speculative Fiction." In *Home Sweat Home: Perspectives on Housework and Modern Relationships*, ed. Elizabeth Patton and Mimi Choi, 69–88. Maryland: Rowman & Littlefield.
- Lee, Mark. 2020. *How to Grow a Robot: Developing Human Friendly, Social AI*. Massachusetts: MIT Press.
- Lin, Patrick, Keith Abney, and George A. Bekey, eds. 2012. *Robot Ethics: The Ethical and Social Implications of Robotics*. Massachusetts: MIT Press.
- Lovelock, James. 2019. *Novacene: The Coming Age of Hyperintelligence*. Massachusetts: MIT Press.
- Mantoux, Paul. 1929. *The Industrial Revolution in the Eighteenth Century: An Outline of the Beginnings of the Modern Factory System in England*, trans. Majorie Vernon. London: Jonathan Cape.
- Marx, Karl. 1990. *Capital: A Critique of Political Economy*, volume 1, trans. Ben Fowkes. St Ives: Penguin Books.
- Marx, Karl. 1993. *Grundrisse: Foundations of the Critique of Political Economy (Rough Draft)*, trans. Martin Nicolaus. London: Penguin Books.
- Mindell, David A. *Our Robots, Ourselves: Robotics and the Myths of Autonomy*. New York: Penguin Random House.
- Mitcham, Carl. 1994. *Thinking Through Technology: The Path Between Engineering and Philosophy*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Mumford, Lewis. *Technics and Civilization*. 1934. London: Routledge & Kegan Paul Ltd.

- Newton, Casey. 2019. "The Trauma Room: The Secret Lives of Facebook Moderators in America." *Verge* February 25, 2019. Accessed April 12, 2021. <https://www.theverge.com/2019/2/25/18229714/cognizant-facebook-content-moderator-interviews-trauma-working-conditions-arizona>.
- Ngai, Sianne. 2020. *Theory of the Gimmick: Aesthetic Theory and Capitalist Form*. Cambridge: Belknap Press.
- Nof, Shimon Y. 2009. "Automation: What it Means to us Around the World." In *Springer Handbook of Automation*. Dordrecht: Springer-Verlag.
- Pickering, Andrew. 1995a. *The Mangle of Practice: Time, Agency and Science*. Chicago: Chicago University Press.
- Pickering, Andrew. 1995b. *Preface to The Mangle of Practice: Time, Agency and Science*. Chicago: Chicago University Press.
- Pickering, Andrew. 2013. "Living in the Material World." In *Materiality and Space: Organizations, Artefacts and Practices*, ed. Francois-Xavier de Vuajany and Nathalie Mitev, 25–40. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Pietz, William. 2003. "Fetish." In *Critical Terms for Art History*, 2nd ed., ed. Robert S. Nelson and Richard Shiff, 306–318. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Read, Max. 2019. "Who Pays for Silicon Valley's Hidden Costs?" *Intelligencer* February 28, 2019. Accessed April 12, 2021. https://nymag.com/intelligencer/amp/2019/02/the-shadow-workforce-of-facebooks-content-moderation.html?__twitter_impression=true.
- Roberts, Sarah T. 2019. *Behind the Screen: Content Moderation in the Shadows of Social Media*. Yale University Press: New Haven.
- Russell, Betrand. 2004. "In Praise of Idleness." In *In Praise of Idleness and Other Essays*, 1–15. London: Routledge.
- Sayes, Edwin Michael. 2013. "Actor-Network Theory and Methodology: Just What Does it Mean to Say That Nonhumans Have Agency?" *Social Studies of Science* 44(1): 134–49.
- Sung, Ja-Young, Rebecca E. Grinter, Henrik I. Christensen, and Lan Guo. 2008. "Housewives or Technophiles: Understanding Domestic Robot Owners." In *HRI 2008 Proceedings*, 129–36. Amsterdam: ACM Press.
- Susskind, Richard, and Daniel Susskind. 2015. *The Future of Professions: How Technology Will Transform the Work of Human Experts*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Taylor, Astra. 2021. "The Automation Charade." *Logic Magazine* 5, August 1, 2018. Accessed April 12, 2021. <https://logicmag.io/failure/the-automation-charade/>.
- Wajcman, Judy. 1991. *Feminism Confronts Technology*. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Wajcman, Judy. 2017. "Automation: Is it Really Different this Time?" *British Journal of Sociology* 68(1): 119–27.